

Original Research

Anomaly Detection for HIDS Using Machine and Deep Learning at Ethiopia's Ministry of Finance

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Received: 22 August 2025

Accepted: 23 August 2025

Published Online: 27 August 2025

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How to cite this article:

Anbessea Nardos Gebru (2025). Anomaly Detection for HIDS Using Machine and Deep Learning at Ethiopia's Ministry of Finance. North American Academic Research, 8(8), 129-144. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17177610>

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Abstract

In today's digital landscape, safeguarding sensitive data, especially in critical sectors like finance, is vital. This study aims to enhance Host Intrusion Detection Systems (HIDS) at Ethiopia's Ministry of Finance using machine learning and deep learning techniques. It compares different methods of supervised and unsupervised learning to identify the most effective method for detecting threats with the Ministry's datasets. Various algorithms, including Random Forest and XGBoost for feature selection, and techniques like SMOTE for imbalanced classes, were employed. In supervised learning, methods like Random Forest, Decision Tree, KNN, XGBoost, Nave Bayes, Logistic Regression and SVM were evaluated. In unsupervised learning, techniques like Isolated Forest, LOF, One-class and SVM were explored. The analysis revealed notable performance, with supervised models achieving perfect accuracy 100%, particularly SVM. The Isolated Forest algorithm stood out in unsupervised learning with a 99% accuracy. Deep learning, especially the denoising autoencoder, showed promising results, achieving a lower Reconstruction error of 0.17.

Keywords: Anomaly Detection, Host-Based Intrusion Detection System, Machine Learning, Supervised Learning, Unsupervised Learning, Cybersecurity.

1. Introduction

Cybersecurity has become a major concern for government and institutional networks because of the rising sophistication and frequency of cyberattacks. In developing countries like Ethiopia, the gap between current defense measures and emerging threats is especially wide. Institutions such as the Ministry of Finance (MOF), which handle sensitive national data and infrastructure, are prime targets for cybercriminals. As traditional security approaches like firewalls and antivirus software fall short, there is an urgent need for smarter, more adaptable defense systems like Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS).

An IDS is a security solution designed to monitor system or network activity to detect signs of unauthorized access, misuse, or unusual behavior. There are two main types: Network-based IDS (NIDS) and Host-based IDS (HIDS). NIDS monitors traffic across the network, while HIDS focuses on individual hosts, making it particularly effective for spotting system-level issues. HIDS can detect abnormal behavior by examining system logs, file changes, and

process activity.

Unlike signature-based detection, which depends on known attack patterns, anomaly detection uses machine learning (ML) to identify deviations from normal behavior. This approach allows for the detection of unknown threats, including zero-day vulnerabilities. Improvements in ML and deep learning have further strengthened the ability of IDS to adapt and learn from changing data patterns.

This paper explores the integration of supervised, unsupervised, and deep learning methods into a hybrid HIDS model designed for the MOF environment. It tackles key challenges such as limited data, computational limits, and the need for solutions tailored to local conditions. The main goal is to create a practical, effective, and adaptable anomaly detection system to improve cybersecurity in resource-limited government systems.

2. Related Works

Anomaly detection in cybersecurity has become an important area of research, especially for Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS). Traditional IDS use signature-based methods that identify known attack patterns by comparing network activity to a set database. While these systems work well for known threats, they struggle to catch new or changing attack methods, often called zero-day attacks. To address this issue, anomaly-based detection methods, often powered by Machine Learning (ML), have gained popularity because they can spot deviations from normal system behavior.

Several studies have looked into ML applications for IDS. Supervised learning algorithms like Decision Trees, Random Forests, and Support Vector Machines (SVM) have shown high detection accuracy when trained on well-labeled datasets. For instance, Xia et al., 2018 reported over 93% accuracy with Random Forests using the NSL-KDD dataset. However, these methods need large amounts of labeled data, which may not be available in real-world environments, such as the Ethiopian MOF network.

Unsupervised learning approaches solve this problem by finding anomalies without needing labeled data. Algorithms like K-Means clustering, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and Isolation Forests can find outliers based on the statistical properties of the data. Ahmed et al., 2016 highlighted that unsupervised models are particularly useful in dynamic environments where attack patterns are continually changing.

Deep learning has also transformed IDS by allowing systems to learn hierarchical representations from raw input data. Techniques like Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks and Autoencoders can model time-based relationships and complex patterns. Kim et al., 2019 showed how effective LSTM is in detecting sequential attack behaviors, achieving top results in anomaly detection tasks.

Despite this progress, most existing IDS research is designed for data-rich, high-resource environments. There is still a gap in applying these techniques to places with limited infrastructure, such as government agencies in developing countries. This paper aims to address that gap by evaluating and combining different ML methods in the context of the Ethiopian Ministry of Finance.

3. Research Gap

The dataset used in this study is sourced directly from Ethiopia's Ministry of Finance, making it a novel and authentic real-world dataset previously unused in academic research. A thorough literature review reveals key limitations of traditional statistical methods in anomaly detection:

- ◆ Dependence on assumptions about data distribution
- ◆ Poor performance with high-dimensional and imbalanced data
- ◆ Limited scalability for large or streaming datasets
- ◆ Weak robustness to noise and non-linear relationships
- ◆ Difficulty adapting to changes or concept drift over time

These challenges highlight the need for more adaptive, scalable, and robust approaches. Machine learning techniques address these gaps, making them more suitable for complex, real-world anomaly detection tasks like those in MOF's infrastructure.

4. Methodology

This study uses three types of machine learning approaches: supervised, unsupervised, and deep learning. These methods aim to create a Host-based Intrusion Detection System (HIDS) designed for the MOF. The process includes data preparation, feature engineering, model selection, training, evaluation, and comparison.

4.1. General Architecture and Workflow

The proposed Host-Based Intrusion Detection System (HIDS) is tailored for deployment within the Ethiopian Ministry of Finance (MOF) to protect sensitive financial data by monitoring endpoint activities and detecting unauthorized behavior. It operates during both control and data transmission phases to ensure data integrity and prevent operational disruptions.

As shown in Figure 3.1, the architecture begins with network traffic filtered by a firewall, followed by analysis through the IDS server. The data undergoes preprocessing removal of missing values, duplicates, and normalization—then passes through dimensionality reduction and feature selection using Random Forest and XGBoost.

The refined dataset is classified as 'Normal' or 'Anomaly' using both:

- ◆ **Supervised learning models:** Random Forest, Decision Tree, SVM, Logistic Regression, KNN, Naive Bayes, and XGBoost.
- ◆ **Unsupervised methods:** Isolation Forest, LOF, One-class SVM, and autoencoders (Denosing, Stacked, Variational).

Figure 1: General Structure of Anomaly Detection in MOF

Figures 2 illustrate the full processing pipeline, from raw data to anomaly detection. The model outputs are evaluated to determine detection accuracy and classify activity accordingly.

Figure 2 : MOF Dataset Processing and Anomaly Detection Workflow

4.2. Research Design and Tool used

This research evaluates machine learning models for Host Intrusion Detection Systems (HIDS) using both supervised

and unsupervised learning. An experimental design compares model performance with a dataset from the Ministry of Finance that includes 22 features and 4,899 instances. The data separates into training and testing sets for supervised classification, while it serves as ground truth for unsupervised anomaly detection. The supervised models are: Random Forest, Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, KNN, SVM, Naive Bayes, and XGBoost. The unsupervised models are: Isolation Forest, LOF, One-Class SVM, and autoencoders (stacked, denoising, variational). Performance is measured with accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, error rate, and speed. For autoencoders, MSE, MAE, MRE, SDRE, threshold, and anomaly count are also included. The visualizations consist of bar charts, KDE plots, and PCA plots. A key limitation is that the dataset focuses on network-level features, leaving out application-level data.

The tools used are: Google Colab (with GPU support), Pandas, NumPy, Scikit-learn, Seaborn, Matplotlib, TensorFlow/Keras, and Time for tracking execution.

4.3. Data Preprocessing

The dataset comprises 22 features and 4,877 instances, exhibiting a class imbalance: 4,047 instances marked as normal (0.0) and 830 as anomalies (1.0). The primary features are as follows: Timestamp, Severity, Host Name, IP Address, Ports, Protocol, Traffic Direction, Application Name, Operating System Type, Event Description, Signature ID, Signature Name, among others.

Data preprocessing included the following steps: in the cleaning stage (handling missing values, and deduplication), encoding of categorical variables (with label or one-hot encoding), and normalization. The imbalance in the target variable was resolved with SMOTE, but only within the training set to prevent data leakage.

Feature selection involved embedded approaches (via Random Forest and XGBoost) to determine importance. Moreover, correlation analysis showed high correlations (Computer Name and Host Name had a 1.0 correlation) which is a sign of redundancy. Based on importance rank thresholds, Severity, Signature ID, and Signature Name contributed substantially, leading to selecting 13 features: Computer Name, Remote Host IP, Signature Name, OS Type, Event Description, Application Name, Severity, Signature ID, Traffic Direction, Host Name, Remote Port, Local Port, Current IP Address.

The aim of this reduced feature set is to improve efficiency, interpretability, and, most importantly, sustain the predictive performance of the model while mitigating overfitting.

Figure 3: Selected Features Based on Score

4.4. Supervised Anomaly Detection

In particular, in this analysis, we adopt various supervised machine learning models for binary classification to recognize anomalies in the MOF dataset. Random Forest, DT, LR, SVM, NB, KNN, and XGBoost are selected as the models for these all have been tested successful in binary classification and used widely for intrusion detection.

Procedure:

Load the Dataset: Use pandas to load the preprocessed dataset. `read_csv()`

Train-Test Split: `train_test_split()` from scikit-learn is used to split data to 80:20 for training and testing datasets.

Initialization of model: All of the classifiers are initialized for comparison.

Training and Prediction: Each model is fit on the training set and the test set is predicted using `fit()` and `predict()` respectively.

Evaluation: The accuracy of a model is calculated with the `accuracy_score()` and compared between models.

Figure 4 Work-flow for the supervised anomaly detection approach. The method allows for an all-round assessment of the model performance on MOF dataset, taking the advantage of strengths of each model in terms of detecting the anomalies.

Figure 4 : Workflow of Selected Classifiers

4.5. Unsupervised Anomaly Detection

We use unsupervised learning methods to find anomalies in a batch dataset provided by the Ministry of Finance with no target, which suggests it is useful for unsupervised analysis. The paper compares all traditional model, Isolation Forest (IF), and Local Outlier Factor (LOF) and One-Class SVM, and deep method of autoencoders (stacked, denoising and variational) used to detect anomalous patterns and potential security threat.

4.5.1. IF, LOF and One-Class SVM Methodology:

Import Libraries: Here I import some of the libraries such as pandas for data manipulation, StandardScaler for scaling and models from sklearn.

Load Data: Loading the preprocessed dataset (13 features) into a DataFrame.

Split: I have split the data 80:20 in `train_test_split` with a consistent random state value so that the results can be reproduced.

Start Timer: We measure the running time by using the time module.

Scale Train Data: The training set is normalized (zero mean, unit variance) using StandardScaler.

Initialization and Training: Each model (IF, LOF, One-Class SVM) is initialized with best parameters (e.g. contamination) and trained on scaled data.

Scale Test Data: We use the same scaler for the test set for same reasons.

Anomaly Scoring & Thresholding: Scores of anomaly scores are calculated; a threshold is determined to assign data points to belonging to normal or anomalous.

Anomaly Labeling: Test data has been labeled with predicted labels (1 for anomaly, -1 or 0 for normal).

Stop Timer - Calculate Time: The total time taken for the execution is noted.

Output Results: The resulting DataFrame with anomaly scores, predictions, and execution time

This process, as described in Figure 3.5, allows for efficient anomaly detection without the need for labeled data. Both effectiveness (as measured by MSE, MAE and detection rate (for autoencoders)) and computational efficiency have been considered for each of the models' performances. The purpose is to improve the risk register and assist in decision-making based on the Ministry's IT system.

Figure 5. Procedure of Unsupervised Anomaly Detection using IF, One-class SVM and LOF

4.6. Auto-Encoder Based Approach for Anomaly Detection

The process of anomaly detection using auto-encoders consists of four steps that can be briefly described as follows (An et al. 2015a). Step 1 (Initialization): In this step, in order to take advantage of the fact that in a tidy dataset from human related activities, every feature dimension can be assumed to be a normal class and every single training sample as negative class where memory is an issue, the size of latent space size is optimized. Unsupervised anomaly detection is performed using three types of autoencoders: denoising, stacked, and Variational Autoencoders (VAE). Every model learns to reconstruct normal samples and to detect anomalies with a high reconstruction error.

Steps:

Load Data: Load data from the processed dataset into a pandas DataFrame.

Initialize Autoencoders:

- ◆ **Stacked Autoencoder:** It takes an encoder (3 Dense layers: 64→32→16, ReLU activation) to compress the input, and a symmetric decoder (16→32→64, sigmoid output) to reconstruct it.
- ◆ **Denoising Autoencoder:** Applies Gaussian noise to the input data, and then trains the model to reconstruct the original clean data, which enhances robustness.
- ◆ **Variational Autoencoder (VAE):** It models a probabilistic latent space. The encoder outputs the mean and log-variance, a sampling layer introduces some noise and the decoder attempts to reconstruct the input given the value sampled from the latent vector.

Train the Model:

Examples are divided into training and test sets.

Models are trained to minimize the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between input and reconstructed output.

Detect Anomalies:

This trained autoencoder re-constructs the test data.

For each instance, the reconstruction error (MSE) is computed.

A cut-off is defined and data points having an error greater than this cut off are considered as anomalies. The high-level view of autoencoder operating is shown in Fig 3.6. This method allows for effective detection of abnormalities from normal behaviors without using labeled data, specifically for intrusion detection in the Ministry of Finance dataset.

Figure 6: General Flow of Autoencoders

5. Evaluation

Performance Evaluation

Performance measures are utilized to measure the performance of intrusion detection machine learning models.

Classification Metrics (for supervised models):

- ◆ **Accuracy:** The number of correct predictions made by the model as a ratio of the total number of cases.
Formula: $(TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN)$
- ◆ **Precision:** Fraction of correctly predicted positives out of all predicted positives.
Formula: $TP / (TP + FP)$
- ◆ **Recall (Sensitivity/TPR):** The percent of actual 'yes' that were predicted correctly.
Formula: $TP / (TP + FN)$
- ◆ **F1-Score:** Harmonic mean of precision and recall to prevent skew from imbalanced data (where one label is more common).
Formula: $2 \times (\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}) / (\text{Precision} + \text{Recall})$
- ◆ **Specificity (TNR):** Ratio of true negatives to total negatives identified.
Formula: $TN / (TN + FP)$
- ◆ **FPR & FNR:** False Positive Rate and False Negative Rate are error rates of detection.

Deep Learning & Reconstruction Metrics (for autoencoders):

- ◆ **MSE (Mean Squared Error):** Mean of squared differences between original and reconstructed values. High MSE may suggest poor model fitting or the presence of outliers.
- ◆ **MAE (Mean Absolute Error):** Average absolute difference between actual and reconstructed values; easier to interpret than MSE.
- ◆ **MRE (Mean Reconstruction Error):** The average reconstruction error used for detecting anomalies. Higher values may indicate potential outliers.
- ◆ **SDRE (Standard Deviation of Reconstruction Error):** Measures how much reconstruction errors vary. High SDRE implies inconsistent reconstructions, which makes threshold setting harder.

These measures allow for a complete assessment of both classification performance and anomaly detection power, even for the case of imbalanced security data.

5.1. Supervised Learning Model Evaluation

The prediction accuracy results of seven different supervised classifiers, including Random Forest, Decision Tree, SVM, Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, KNN and XGBoost, are illustrated in Figure 7. The bar graph indicates outstanding accuracy levels of all models with multiple models achieving nearly 100% score. This shows that the models are quite good at classifying the data point between normal and anomaly when kept preprocessed and balanced (by SMOTE). The high accuracy indicates that the features and pre-processing used can actually make a significant contribution to the learning and generalization capabilities.

Figure 7: Supervised Model Classifiers Evaluation

Supervised Learning Model Summary

Seven supervised machine learning algorithms Random Forest, Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, KNN, XGBoost, and SVM are compared with different metrics and visualizations.

Classification Rates shown in Table 5.1.1 summarized as:

- ◆ **Random Forest, Logistic Regression, XGBoost, and SVM** deliver perfect classification performance: TP Rate = 1, TN Rate = 1, FP Rate = 0, FN Rate = 0
This means no false positives or false negatives—indicating flawless results.
- ◆ **Decision Tree** shows slightly lower performance with a TP Rate of 0.994 and FN Rate of 0.006, suggesting minimal misclassification.
- ◆ **Naive Bayes** and **KNN** also perform very well, with a minor FP Rate of 0.0012 and TN Rate of 0.999—indicating very few false alarms.

Table 5.1.1: Evaluation Metrics of Different Models

Model	TP Rate	FP Rate	TN Rate	FN Rate
Random Forest	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.000
Decision Tree	0.994	0.000	1.000	0.006
Logistic Regression	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.000
Naive Bayes	1.000	0.0012	0.999	0.000
KNN	1.000	0.0012	0.999	0.000
XGBoost	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.000
SVM	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.000

ROC Curve Analysis (Figure 8):

- ◆ All classifiers achieve a perfect AUC of 1.00.

- ◆ The ROC curves stay close to the top-left corner, confirming a near-ideal balance between true positive rate (sensitivity) and false positive rate (specificity).

Figure 8: Roc Curve for Different Classifiers

Execution Time and Error Rate (Table 5.1.2):

Fastest Models:

Decision Tree: 0.0078 sec

Naive Bayes: 0.0067 sec

Slowest Model:

XGBoost: 32.715 sec, due to its ensemble complexity

Error Rates:

Random Forest, Logistic Regression, SVM, and XGBoost all have 0 error rate.

Decision Tree, Naive Bayes, and KNN have a minimal error rate of 0.001.

Table 5.1.2: Execution Time and Error Rate of Anomaly Models (80%-20%)

Anomaly Model	Execution Time (sec)	Error Rate
Random Forest	0.6771	0.000
Decision Tree	0.0078	0.001
Logistic Regression	0.6762	0.000
Naive Bayes	0.0067	0.001
KNN	0.0600	0.001
XGBoost	32.7150	0.000
SVM	0.0375	0.000

Model Robustness Across

Data Splits (Table 5.1.3):

Classifier	90/10	80/20	70/30	60/40
Random Forest	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Decision Tree	1.000	0.998	0.9993	0.9994
Logistic Regression	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.999
Naive Bayes	1.000	0.998	0.9993	0.998
KNN	1.000	0.998	0.9993	0.999
XGBoost	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
SVM	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Decision Tree, Naive Bayes, and KNN show slight variations (accuracy ≥ 0.998) but remain highly dependable.

Learning Curves (Figures 9 & 10):

SVM maintains a perfect training score while validation scores improve, confirming strong generalization and learning ability.

Random Forest shows steady improvement in both training and validation scores as data increases, indicating effective learning with no signs of overfitting.

Figure 9: Random Forest Learning Curve

Figure 10: SVM Learning Curve

Conclusion:

The supervised models, especially Random Forest, Logistic Regression, SVM, and XGBoost, achieve exceptional accuracy, perfect AUC, and strong robustness across multiple data splits. Although XGBoost is the slowest, it records zero error. Simpler models like Decision Tree and Naive Bayes are fastest but carry slightly higher error rates. Overall, the models' high performance is attributed to solid pre-processing, feature selection, and the use of SMOTE for data balancing.

Figure 11: Classifiers with Different Proportion of Training and Test Set

5.2. Evaluation of the Unsupervised Learning Model

In this section we compare our hypothesis to three unsupervised anomaly detection models: Isolation Forest, One-Class SVM and Local Outlier Factor under various evaluation strategies, namely pseudo-supervised metrics on labeled data (treated as ground truth) and performance on training splits.

Key Evaluation Approaches:

Unsupervised With Ground Truth: Supervised learning labels are employed to calculate classification metrics.

Training-Test Split Performance: Models are evaluated on an 80:20 train-test split.

Visualization: PCA plot, AUC plot, and gain plot are the techniques to understand the model.

Summary of Results

1. Performance on 80:20 Split

Table 5.2.1: Performance Evaluation

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall (TPR)	F1-Score	TNR	FPR	FNR
Isolation Forest	99%	94%	98%	96%	98%	2%	2%
One-Class SVM	98%	90%	100%	95%	97%	2%	0%
LOF	77%	41%	35%	38%	88%	12%	65%

- ◆ Isolation Forest: Most balanced performer with high accuracy, precision, recall, and low error rates.
- ◆ One-Class SVM: Best recall (100%), ideal for high-sensitivity scenarios; slightly lower precision.
- ◆ LOF: Significantly underperforms across all metrics, indicating poor fit for this dataset.

Figure 11: Roc-Curve for Anomaly Detection Models in 0.2 split

2. Evaluation Against Ground Truth (Figure 12)

- ◆ Isolation Forest again outperforms others in effectiveness (high accuracy, F1, recall) and efficiency (fastest execution).
- ◆ One-Class SVM has high TNR but very low TPR and recall, meaning it misses many anomalies.
- ◆ LOF performs poorly overall, with high FNR and low precision/recall.

Figure 12: Roc-Curve for Anomaly Detection Models (IF, LOF and One-class SVM)

Conclusion

- ◆ Isolation Forest is the top-performing unsupervised model, offering high accuracy, balanced precision-recall, low error rates, and fast execution.
- ◆ One-Class SVM is excellent at minimizing false negatives (high recall) but suffers in precision.
- ◆ LOF is not well-suited for this dataset, showing poor detection capability and high misclassification rates.

5.3. Evaluation for Deep Learning Autoencoders

This section evaluates three deep learning autoencoder models Stacked, Denoising, and Variational Autoencoders for unsupervised anomaly detection using two approaches: comparison against ground truth labels and reconstruction error analysis.

1. Performance Against Ground Truth (Table 5.3.1)

Autoencoder	Accuracy	F1-Score	Precision	Recall	Time (sec)
Stacked	0.85	0.26	0.94	0.26	10.2
Denoising	0.91	0.64	0.99	0.47	13.5
Variational	0.85	0.26	0.94	0.15	11

- ◆ Denoising Autoencoder outperforms the others in accuracy, F1-score, precision, and recall, indicating superior balance in detecting anomalies while minimizing false positives.
- ◆ Both Stacked and Variational autoencoders show high precision but very low recall, meaning they miss many anomalies.
- ◆ Denoising AE takes longer to train (13.5 sec) but delivers significantly better detection performance.

2. Reconstruction-Based Metrics (Table 5.3.2)

Metric	Stacked	Denoising	Variational
MSE	0.69	0.7	0.69
MAE	0.39	0.41	0.39
Mean Reconstruction Error	0.69	0.17	1
SD of Reconstruction Error	2	0.11	2.49
Threshold	4.7	0.4	5.9
Number of Anomalies Detected	134	399	134

- ◆ Denoising Autoencoder excels with the lowest mean and standard deviation of reconstruction error, indicating consistent and accurate reconstructions of normal data.
- ◆ It uses a much lower threshold (0.4), making it more sensitive to anomalies.
- ◆ It detects 399 anomalies, far more than the 134 detected by the other two models, suggesting better sensitivity.
- ◆ Stacked and Variational models show similar behavior, with higher and more variable reconstruction errors.

Key Visualizations

Figure 13 (Anomaly Detection Plot):

- ◆ Shows reconstruction error on the y-axis.
- ◆ Blue dots (normal) cluster at low error; red dots (anomalies) lie above a threshold line.
- ◆ Confirms that anomalies are spread throughout the dataset and are effectively separated by error magnitude

Figure 13: Anomaly Detection using Denoising Autoencoder

Figure 14 (KDE Plot):

- ◆ Kernel Density Estimate of reconstruction errors for training and test sets.
- ◆ Nearly identical distributions (blue and green curves) indicate good generalization.
- ◆ Peak near zero error shows the model reconstructs most data accurately.
- ◆ No signs of overfitting; model performs consistently on unseen data.

Figure 14: KDE Plot of Reconstruction Error

Figure 15 (Training Curve):

- ◆ Training and validation loss decrease sharply and then converge smoothly over 100 epochs.
- ◆ Parallel curves indicate no overfitting and stable learning.
- ◆ Validates that the denoising autoencoder learns effectively and generalizes well.

Figure 15: Error Rate Learning curve for Denoising Autoencoder

Conclusion

- ◆ The Denoising Autoencoder is the best-performing model among the three, demonstrating:
 - ◆ Highest F1-score and accuracy against ground truth.
 - ◆ Lowest and most consistent reconstruction errors.
 - ◆ Ability to detect significantly more anomalies.
- ◆ Stacked and Variational autoencoders underperform due to poor recall and higher error variability.
- ◆ Visualization tools (scatter plot, KDE, loss curves) confirm the reliability and generalization capability of the denoising model.

6. Conclusion

This study presents an empirical evaluation of anomaly detection techniques for Host-Based Intrusion Detection Systems (HIDS), specifically designed for the Ministry of Finance in Ethiopia. It uses ensemble feature selection (Random Forest, XGBoost), handles class imbalance with SMOTE, and evaluates both supervised and unsupervised models.

- ◆ Supervised Models: Random Forest, XGBoost, and SVM achieved high accuracy, with SVM standing out for its computational efficiency.
- ◆ Unsupervised Models: Isolation Forest outperformed One-Class SVM and LOF across all metrics.
- ◆ Deep Learning: Among autoencoders, the Denoising Autoencoder proved most effective, with low reconstruction error and superior anomaly detection.

The study demonstrates that carefully selected and optimized models can significantly enhance intrusion detection performance.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

7. Future Work

1. Expand Dataset: Include authentication, system, and application logs for richer behavioral analysis.
2. Integrate Multi-Source Data: Combine data from firewalls, NIDS, and EDR systems for comprehensive threat detection.
3. Explore Semi-Supervised Learning: Leverage partially labeled data to improve real-world applicability.
4. Integrate with Security Systems: Combine the framework with existing misuse detection systems for stronger, hybrid security.

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